

PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH SKILLS IN STUDENTS BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *Research activity contributes to the comprehensive formation of a person, improves the development of students and, of course, the indicators of mental activity.*

The article highlights the principles of developing research skills in students based on an innovative approach in order to identify problems and needs of students, find new solutions, develop and test new products and services, analyze marketing strategies and competition.

Keywords: *approach, problem, need, solution, product, service, marketing, competition, plan, strategy, approach.*

Innovative approach is the pursuit of continuous development, efforts to search for new and unique solutions that improve the quality of work processes, products and services, and increase the company's competitiveness in the market.

The main goal of the innovative approach in education is to identify problems and needs of students, find new solutions, develop and test new products and services, analyze marketing strategies and competition. For this, it is necessary to create an effective management system, improve the qualifications of teachers, develop action plans and strategies, automate and integrate work processes.

An innovative approach allows you to achieve educational goals and take a leading position. But for this, it is necessary to always be ready to keep up with the times, follow development trends and quickly respond to changes in the external environment.

Extracurricular activities play a major role in developing students' research skills based on an innovative approach. Extracurricular activities create favorable conditions for the development of students' potential, as a result of which the student expands knowledge, acquires, enriches research skills and experiences in the fields of interest.

It is known that the scope of the traditional lesson is limited, the ability to use various resources when working with students does not contribute to the full disclosure of student abilities. If extracurricular activities for developing research skills in students based on an innovative approach are built on the principles of free choice, reciprocity, psychological comfort, they will update students' research skills, increase research opportunities, form joint activities, knowledge acquisition and interest in research.

Research activities contribute to the comprehensive formation of a person, the development of students and, of course, the indicators of mental activity (the ability to classify objects, generalize, consider them from different points of view, compare different objects and their sum, as well as assign tasks on the proposed topic and self-control) improves. According to A.P. Gladkova, the concept of "research" should be considered together with the categories "research skills", "research behavior", "research activity", "educational-research activity" [1].

The appropriateness of using these categories is based on the following principles:

- research behavior, which by its nature is the main need of a person;

- research activity, which is the basis of research behavior, as well as research activity;
- one of the types of research activity - specially organized study-research, educational-creative activity of the student [1].

According to A.I. Savenkov, in our everyday imagination, a researcher is usually called a person who conducts scientific research [2]. Studies conducted by physiologists show that research activities significantly increase the body's resistance to the effects of various harmful factors. In addition, it is important that this effect is almost independent of the nature of the emotions that accompany the act of searching. Research activity is the driving force of individual self-development.

According to O.A. Ivashova, research activity is manifested in the following [3]:

- development of students' cognitive skills and abilities;
- the ability to navigate in the information space;
- the ability to design one's knowledge independently;
- ability to integrate knowledge from different fields of science;
- critical thinking ability [3].

According to M.I. Makhmutov, the following tasks are performed in the research activities:

1) to activate and update the knowledge acquired by students in studying a specific subject; systematization of knowledge; familiarization with a set of materials that go beyond the scope of the educational program. 2) imagine, analyze, compare the content of the studied topic, draw one's own conclusions; material selection and arrangement; use of ICT in research design; public presentation of research results. 3) creating a product that is interesting and demanded by others [4].

Organization of research activities, selection and analysis of available data, independent selection and application of research methods and methods that ensure the achievement of the desired result are important in developing research skills in students based on an innovative approach. It includes seeing problems, developing hypotheses, observing, conducting experiments, defining concepts, obtaining information, conducting independent research, comparing, evaluating, proving the correctness of a point of view, and making an internal plan of mental actions; the formation of judgments is carried out step by step.

Research skills are the success of forming and implementing previously acquired skills, a set of operations that is a method of performing mental and practical actions (including creative research actions) that make up research activities.

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